

Pulsating Circle

Circle Translation

Rotating Ellipse

Circle Ellipse Transformation

Stretching/Shrinking Circle

Inward Membrane Changes

Outward Membrane Changes

Single Protrusion

Neighboring Protrusions

Distant Protrusions

Local dispersion ($\frac{1}{s}$)

Local motion ($\frac{\mu\text{m}}{s}$)

Curvature ($\frac{1}{\mu\text{m}}$)

Different Sized Protrusions

Local dispersion ($\frac{1}{s}$)

Local motion ($\frac{\mu\text{m}}{s}$)

Curvature ($\frac{1}{\mu\text{m}}$)

Protrusions During Translation I

Protrusions During Translation II

